

1 Gene products induced in human cells by Shigella.

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7 We defined here a minimal set of genes regulated by Shigella infection by measuring total transcription in
8 HeLa cells with RNA-sequencing following infection with Shigella flexneri. We found induction of Sod2
9 within hours of infection *in vitro*. The oxidized lipoprotein receptor OLR1 was a major target of Shigella
10 infection in human cells, as were the TNF superfamily regulatory proteins TNFAIP1 and TNFAIP2. The
11 nucleic acid sensor RIG-I was rapidly activated by infection with this diarrhea-inducing bacterial agent.
12 Shigella infection activated interferon stimulated genes including IFIT2 and IFIT3, the receptor FNDCB, and
13 activated production of CCL20. Zc3hav1, also known as the zinc finger antiviral protein (ZAP) was not
14 specific to cellular activation following infection with a diarrhea-inducing virus and was also a
15 transcriptional hallmark of Shigella infection.

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17 Citations

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